

EL LLIT NOU DEL POYO

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60m
40m
20m

diversity
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 Flash-Flood-Induced Changes in the Hydrochemistry of the Albufera of Valencia Coastal Lagoon
 Juan M. Soria, Rafael Muñoz, Noelia Campillo, Tamara: Juan Victor Molner
 Diversity 2025, Volume 17, Issue 2, 119

water
 an Open Access Journal by MDPI
 Estimating Peak Flows in Streams During the Flash Flood Event of 29 October 2024 in Spain: An Empirical Approach
 Rafael Muñoz, Juan Victor Molner, Noelia Campillo, Tamara: Juan Soria
 Water 2025, Volume 17, Issue 21, 3177

SECCIÓN MOJADA = 1120 m²
 CAUDAL = 1120 m³/s

SECCIÓN MOJADA = 12 m²
 CAUDAL = 12 m³/s

SECCIÓN MOJADA = 2271,66 m²
 CAUDAL = 2271,66 m³/s

CAUDAL DE=1120 m² x 3 m/s=3360 m³/s